

A STUDY OF USERS' EMOTIONAL EXPERIENCES FOR COMMUNITY CULTURAL PRODUCTS USING KANO MODEL

I-Chia Tsai¹, Shyh-Huei Hwang²
Graduate School of Design Doctoral Program,
National Yunlin University of Science and Technology, Yunlin, Taiwan
beckey.tsai@gmail.com¹, hwangsh@yuntech.edu.tw²

ABSTRACT

With all of the possible diverse and peculiar visual patterns, it is essential that designers offer products of value; cultural products should reflect a high quality of design based on the emotional experiences that consumers experience with these products. Research on the emotional experiences derived from cultural products has increasingly focused upon both museum products and products produced in large quantities. The aim of this paper was to explore how emotional experiences and user relationships are related and how a user's emotional experiences may be elicited from community cultural products. This research used the Kano Model to determine the preferences and satisfaction of users and to determine the emotional experiences resulting from community cultural products. The high level of involvement of 62 people in the community study produced both positive and negative questionnaire results. A quantitative analysis of the questionnaires focused on users' needs as related to cultural products. The results of this study revealed that users are generally satisfied with hand-made items which reflect the cultural values of a community, and that good feelings result from travel experiences. In addition, the results provide designers with a better understanding of how to design suitable products.

Keywords: Users' Emotional Experiences, Community Cultural Products, Kano Quality Attributes

INTRODUCTION

User satisfaction increases as positive emotions are experienced. In recent years, the related design references have focused on evoking emotional experiences or affective emotions, especially as related to cultural products in museums or mass-produced cultural products, such as figure dolls¹ and the Jadeite Cabbage in the National Palace Museum.²

However, multi-cultural Taiwan has many unique community industries founded on the original works of craftsmen or artists, and community industries not only improve local residents' spiritual meaning of life but also inherit the cultural value of products (Chen, 1995). A product produced in the community, focusing on local cultural elements and using local materials and images, can employ creative methods to create emotional experiences for users. Furthermore, a small quantity of community cultural products will need more qualities to enhance each of these emotional experiences in order to recognize requirements of community cultural products. Through users' preferences and emotional experiences, this paper aimed to determine the difference of normal products and community cultural products to derive the essential features of community cultural product.

THE RELATION BETWEEN USERS' EMOTIONAL EXPERIENCE AND THE KANO MODEL

The key factors behind the development of a creative industry (Hwang, 2002) are: story, aesthetic perception, value, creation and experiences which produce empathy with the local cultural identity. These factors allow users to comprehend the inner meaning of the design. Products contain the identification of local culture and external factors; these affect users in regard to their purchases and their satisfaction with the cultural products produced within a community. In relation to satisfaction and quality, most research is based on one-dimension, increasing quality; this means that increased requirements of product quality will be reflected in enhanced user satisfaction. Conversely, when requirements of product quality are reduced, user dissatisfaction will increase. However, according to Kano (2001), the theory of attractive quality originated because of the lack of explanatory power of a one-dimensional recognition of quality.

When the product conforms to the satisfaction of consumers, or when the provision of product quality is taken for granted, the enhancement of quality cannot affect satisfaction. Kano (1984) proposed “psychological quality” as the central concept of the Kano Model, i.e., that users’ expectations will directly affect users’ satisfaction. He considered that users’ satisfaction and the quality of products are subject to levels of degree as perceived by users. In the Kano model, there are five different quality classifications: Attractive quality, One-dimensional quality, Must-be quality, Indifferent quality and Reversal quality (Kano, 1984). This paper focuses on the quality of community cultural products using the Kano Model to discuss the related user satisfaction and the quality of community cultural products. The aim of this paper was to investigate and better define the requirements and quality of community cultural products and planned product quality characteristics reflecting community culture. In so doing, this paper aimed to contribute to a general understanding of the qualities in community cultural products that can stimulate new design directions and enhance competitiveness within community industries.

COMMUNITY INDUSTRY

Improving culture, eco-environmental quality and the visual landscape, as well as maintaining family livelihood and increasing local employment are the goals of community revitalization. In recent years, Taiwan government’s guidance policy for promoting community cultural industries has attempted to determine cultural properties that employ value-added culture through marketing practices promoted by industrial restructuring and upgrading. Designers and craftsmen have helped to create high-quality local industrial development, regenerating the local economy because of their affection for community culture. Community industries, such as black tea of Sun Moon Lake³ are rooted in the local environment with local characteristics, and recognize that the cultural and historical records of users and community experience are based on community life.

THE FUNCTIONALITY OF COMMUNITY INDUSTRY

Community industry has promoted the preservation of community culture and the reconstruction of

original environments for the benefit of both tourists and local residents. The historical and ecological development of communities is displayed in cultural centers whose purpose is to convey both visible and invisible aspects of shared living within a community. Currently, increasingly diverse community and cultural products are being presented which evoke a variety of emotional experiences and product purchase intention. Corresponding to this diversity of materials, images and design features, is a trend toward emotional consumption among modern users. This reflects the human need for meaning, a need that the cultural creative industries recognize and intend to meet. Accordingly, the development of these industries has been characterized by an emphasis on five elements (Hwang, 2002): stories, aesthetics, value, creation and experience. In stories, a community’s historical culture is depicted and the spirit of the place and persons is presented. In aesthetics, attention is drawn to the shape of an object, i.e., its form and appeal, which leads to attraction and a desire to possess such an object. In terms of value, cultural industries concentrate on the recognition of product value, thereby meeting the demand for utilitarian products. In creativity, fresh products bring something new and surprising to the human experience. Finally, in experience, the focus is on depth, which is conveyed through the services and activities that heighten the user’s sense of attachment.

COMMUNITY CULTURAL PRODUCT

According to UNESCO, “Cultural products refer to those products which can communicate opinions, symbols, and lifestyle” (Council for Cultural Affairs, 2003). Achieving creative design is based on a large number of copyrights involving industrial processes and global distribution; these were acquired to promote the creation of cultural products. The community culture industry is defined as being based on creativity, individuality (personalized products), local traditions, local specialty and the original work of craftsman or artists, all of which underline product value and the spiritual meaning of life (Chen, 1995). There are differences between culture products and community cultural products; community cultural products stress hand-made co-production by community group, local characteristics,

creativity by local residents, and so on. Community industry is often derived from the initiative of its citizens, particular groups of individuals, or from specific local conditions. Community cultural products not only develop and restore local industry, but also create employment opportunities, thereby reducing unemployment. The features of different products may be summarized as follows:

Product	Product features
 General Bag	Normal product: Functional products
 Blue lotus pattern bag in National Palace Museum	Cultural product: Functional products with cultural elements and features
 Plant Dyeing bag in Nantou County ⁴	Community cultural product: Functional and empirical products with local cultural elements, features, and materials, especially in creativity by local residents.

Table1: The classification of product.

PRODUCT EMOTIONAL EXPERIENCE

Experiences involve perceived goodness or badness, pleasantness or unpleasantness (Desmet, & Hekkert, 2007); attractive things seem to appeal more (Norman, 2005) and generate positive feelings when used, and things that work better tend to be more attractive to users (Uchida, 2009). User needs and user experiences influence their choice of products, which is the main reason designers like product attributes that correspond to user demand. Demir, E. & Desmet, P.M.A. (2009) noted five elements that relate to the emotional experience of products: (1) noticing of a product; (2) an event occurring during product usage; (3) an entire usage episode; (4) an external agent mentioning the product; and (5) a change in the relationship between a user and a product. Product design takes all five elements into account, thus, including not only the creative imagination of the designer, but also users' lifestyle and cultural influences on the design of the product

(De Souza & Dejean, 1998). Designers deeply involved in their products investigate community imagination and culture before designing a community cultural product. They observe cultural life, ecology and the history in the community in an effort to excite user resonance and satisfy users' emotional needs.

Users use community cultural products to obtain emotional experiences: subjective expression of feelings, response reaction and physiological reactions. Through past experiences, users seek community cultural products to evoke aesthetic perceptions and generate meaning. These products create emotional experiences and cultural identification through immersion in community emotions. The behavior of users in the purchase of community cultural products is as follows (Hwang, 2002):

- (1) Consumption involving practical considerations: These users consider whether or not products meet their practical requirements.
- (2) Consumption involving aesthetic considerations: These users consider uniqueness, shape, materials and decoration of products; e.g. red brick adornment of Miao-li County⁵, etc.
- (3) Consumption involving ethical considerations: When users buy some community cultural products, the point of shopping is to help the operation and development of the community; these users do not usually care about the price, practice and appealing shape of products but rather the underlying community stories.

Product design which engenders emotions affects products through the link between the emotional communication and users' emotional motivation. Product design does not only involve the knowledge and imagination of designers, but also users' lifestyles and the cultural background of the product (De Souza & Dejean, 1998). Before designing a community cultural product, designers have to investigate the imagination and story of the community, observing lifestyle, eco-environmental quality and visual landscape. Moreover, the users' emotional involvement in the community results

from communication before and after use, and from emotional experiences that are passed on through community cultural products.

KANO THEORY

In order to amend traditional cognition in the one-dimensional quality of a product or service to clarify user ideas, Kano and his co-workers developed the theory of attractive quality (Kano et al., 1984). The theory recognizes that invisible ideas about quality can be made visible and can help one to better understand how users evaluate and perceive quality attributes. The theory of attractive quality explains the relationship between the degree of sufficiency and user satisfaction with a quality attribute, especially if it can be classified into one of the five categories of perceived quality: 1) attractive quality; 2) must-be quality; 3) reverse quality; 4) one-dimensional quality; and 5) indifferent quality.

Figure 1: Kano Diagram.

- **Attractive quality:** Attractive quality attributes can be described as attributes of surprise and delight; they provide satisfaction when achieved fully, but do not cause dissatisfaction when not fulfilled (Kano et al., 1984; Martin & Lars, 2005). For example, quality of community cultural products is meant to please users.
- **One-dimensional quality:** One-dimensional quality attributes result in satisfaction when fulfilled and dissatisfaction when unfulfilled. Figure 1 shows a linear level of satisfaction from the lower left to the upper right (Kano et al., 1984; Martin & Lars, 2005). For example, if a community cultural product can cater to more user requirements, users will be more

satisfied, but if it provides fewer requirements, users will be disappointed.

- **Must-be quality:** Must-be quality attributes are taken for granted when fulfilled but result in dissatisfaction when unfulfilled (Kano et al. 1984). These attributes can be represented by the material a product is made from. Users are satisfied when community cultural products are made of local or natural materials; if this is not the case, the result will be diminished user satisfaction.
- **Indifferent quality:** Indifferent quality refers to aspects that users consider neutral; they do not result in either user satisfaction or dissatisfaction.
- **Reverse quality:** Reverse quality refers to when product quality is sufficient yet this result in decreased satisfaction; conversely, when product quality is not sufficient, yet the result is increased consumer satisfaction.

The theory of attractive quality predicts that product attributes are dynamic; that is, over time an attribute will change from being indifferent, to attractive, to one-dimensional, or to must-be.

THE ESTABLISHMENT OF KANO QUALITY ATTRIBUTES

The classification of Kano quality attributes described previously is based on a series of two-way questions. The quality attributes were extracted from a pair of questions: one asked what a user's satisfaction level is when the quality of product is sufficient, and the other asked what a user's satisfaction level is when the quality of product is insufficient. The options for answers include: "I like it that way", "It must be that way", "I am neutral", "I can live with it that way", and "I dislike it that way." Each quality attribute can be classified into one of the six categories shown in Table 2.

user Requirements	dysfunctional					
		like	must be	neutral	live with	dislike
functional	like	Q	A	A	A	O
	must be	R	I	I	I	M
	neutral	R	I	I	I	M
	live with	R	I	I	I	M
	dislike	R	R	R	R	Q

(A=attractive, M=must be, O=one-dimensional, I=indifferent, R=reverse, Q=questionable)

Table 2: Kano evaluation table.

The category “questionable” contains skeptical answers, and it is debatable whether the respondent has understood the question (Kano et al. 1984). Cells 2-2 and 4-4 in the Kano evaluation table were changed from “I” to “Q,” since they believe, for example, that a requirement that is rated as must-be functional cannot simultaneously be rated as must-be dysfunctional. Kano (1984) classifies five combinations of the 25 options as questionable. Through the Kano evaluation table, the quality attributes calculation times in six classifications, and the maximum number is represented by the number of quality attributes. Besides, the user satisfaction coefficient derived through the questionnaire can be interpreted as to whether sufficient or insufficient quality has an effect on user satisfaction and dissatisfaction. The questionnaire results also indicate “the extent of satisfaction” and “extent of dissatisfaction” of each quality by (a) and (b) formula. When the extent of satisfaction is close to 1, it represents the product as being of a quality where user satisfaction could be easily improved. Extent of dissatisfaction is shown as being closest to -1; it represents a product where less quality will reduce user satisfaction.

Extent of satisfaction: $(A + O)/(A + O + M + I)$ (a)

Extent of dissatisfaction: $-1(O + M)/(A + O + M + I)$ (b)

Kano theory is applied to understanding the users' emotional experience and the requirements of community cultural products. Community cultural products, where elements need to be attractive, must-be more and better able to satisfy users' needs. The research data indicate that these different qualities of community cultural products should relate to different levels of satisfaction and quality needs, as well as to provide designers with a deeper understanding of how to better devise products based upon positive user experiences.

METHOD

In this section the empirical investigation of how users perceive community cultural products is

described using the Kano Model to ascertain the relationship between quality and satisfaction. Through the questionnaire of the Kano Model, this paper investigates the quality requirements of community cultural products to assist in future product design and development. The experimental design research is described as follows:

EMOTIONAL EXPERIENCE AND QUALITY OF COMMUNITY CULTURAL PRODUCTS

The elements of desirable community cultural products were determined through literature review and interviews whereby users' feelings about the community experience of cultural products were collected. In the literature, Demir, E. & Desmet, P.M.A. (2009) noted five elements that relate to the emotional experience of products and Hwang, S. H. (2002) identified three behaviours regarding consumption of community cultural products. From these, general user behavior in buying community cultural products was determined. Emotional experience elements of community cultural product can be inferred in the review of the related literature. Moreover, the five interviewees in this study include those with a design background who expressed a high level of motivation to take part in community activities. The procedure followed is described below:

1. Before performing the user interview, we prepared picture cards depicting cultural products characteristic of the community. These picture cards, which included 100 pieces, were from the “Exhibition of the community and local cultural centers” held by the Council for Cultural Affairs, Republic of China (Taiwan). After sorting out the non-food and functional products, a total of 60 pieces were chosen.
2. Questions asked during the interview included the following: “Have you ever bought or seen community cultural products? Please give three examples.” “What was the expected performance of the product, and how did this affect your mood?” “What emotions were involved in the selection process?” “What emotional changes took place after the purchase?”
3. We asked subjects to pick their top 3 favorites from among the 60 picture cards. Subjects were

able to understand the names and sources of the products from the picture cards, and all of the picture cards were presented randomly. Five interviewers selected 11 cultural products from all the products and used these as a sample of community cultural products in the questionnaire.

1	2	3
Wedding Candle Holder ⁶	Brick Card Set ⁷	Flower Light ⁸
4	5	6
Impatiens Package ⁹	Bark Lamp ¹⁰	Spice Jar ¹¹
7	8	9
Bowl with Chopsticks ¹²	Brick Charm ¹³	Art Cup ¹⁴
10	11	
Health Massager ¹⁵	Rush Pillow ¹⁶	

Table 3: Community cultural product samples.

- We then surveyed the subjects to estimate their preference in terms of cultural products and had them illustrate their purchase reasons in order to construct items for evaluation. These reasons would be elements of community cultural products in Kano questionnaire.
- Finally, 10 pre-testers who are students in the design department filled in the Kano Model questionnaire. Indifferent qualities in the elements were eliminated and attractive, must-be, and one-dimensional qualities were selected elements related to the emotional

experience of users using or possessing community cultural products.

QUESTIONNAIRE OF KANO QUALITY ATTRIBUTES

The questionnaire was divided into three parts: background questions, sentiment investigation and quality investigation of community cultural products.

1. Background question: This includes gender, age, education, how many times the respondent travelled to the community, and so on.

2. Sentiment investigation: This part aimed to survey users' affective experience. Using emotion-related adjective sampling and community cultural product images (see Table 3), we tried to understand the users' emotional reflections when they possessed or used community cultural products.

3. Quality investigation of community cultural products. The third part of the quality investigation was concerned with positive quality and negative quality (see Figure 2). The theory of attractive quality classified the 25 quality attributes. The Kano survey is depicted in Table 2, with one result representing the count of how many measurements fall into a single state according to the evaluation table into either attractive (A), one-dimensional (O), must-be (M), indifferent (I), reverse (R), or questionable (Q).

When element is sufficient, how do you feel ^a		Elements of community cultural products ^a					When element is insufficient, how do you feel ^a				
like ^a	must be ^a	neutral ^a	live with ^a	dislike ^a		like ^a	must be ^a	neutral ^a	live with ^a	dislike ^a	
0	0	0	0	0	Appearing shape ^a	0	0	0	0	0	
0	0	0	0	0	Uniqueness ^a	0	0	0	0	0	
0	0	0	0	0	functionality ^a	0	0	0	0	0	

Figure 2: Questionnaire of Kano Attractive Quality.

OUR SUBJECTS

The subjects who filled in the questionnaires included 26 men and 36 women between 18 and 39 years of age who expressed a high level of motivation for taking part in community activities. All of the subjects were from the design department of universities.

RESULTS

	The elements of community cultural product	A(%)	O(%)	M(%)	I(%)	R(%)	CS	DS	classification
Noticing a	Appealing shape	32.3	27.4	25.8	14.5	0.0	0.60	-0.53	A

Product	Uniqueness	33.9	19.4	27.4	17.7	1.6	0.54	-0.48	A
	Nostalgia	22.6	9.7	6.5	61.3	0.0	0.32	-0.16	I
	Quality	21.0	38.7	21.0	19.4	0.0	0.60	-0.60	O
	Pleasure	40.3	11.3	12.9	35.5	0.0	0.52	-0.24	A
	Creativity	41.9	25.8	9.7	21.0	0.0	0.69	-0.36	A
	Plain	22.6	8.1	6.5	62.9	0.0	0.31	-0.15	I
	Traditional style	24.2	4.8	6.5	64.5	0.0	0.29	-0.11	I
an event occurring during product usage	Functionality	33.9	1.6	17.7	46.8	0.0	0.35	-0.19	I
	My need	11.3	14.5	12.9	59.7	1.6	0.26	-0.28	I
an entire usage episode	Local element and features	25.8	12.9	35.5	25.8	0.0	0.39	-0.48	M
	Include Taiwan style	24.2	9.7	3.2	62.9	0.0	0.34	-0.13	I
	Natural material	43.5	9.7	4.8	40.3	0.0	0.54	-0.15	A
An external agent mentioning the product	After listening to a tour guide and learning about local culture and story	16.1	1.6	6.5	71.0	3.2	0.19	-0.08	I
	Quality assurance	6.5	29.0	40.3	24.2	0.0	0.35	-0.69	M
	External propaganda	6.5	1.6	8.1	79.0	4.8	0.08	-0.10	I
A change in the relationship	Value of collection	32.3	14.5	22.6	30.6	0.0	0.47	-0.37	A
	Memory of traveling	17.7	21.0	21.0	40.3	0.0	0.39	-0.42	I
	Adornment	11.3	4.8	11.3	71.0	0.0	0.16	-0.16	I
	Commemorative value	11.3	17.7	40.3	30.6	0.0	0.29	-0.58	M
	Hand-made by the craftsmen and artists	51.6	8.1	1.6	38.7	0.0	0.60	-0.10	A
	Hand-made by myself	46.8	8.1	4.8	38.7	1.6	0.56	-0.13	A
	Be a souvenir	25.8	4.8	3.2	64.5	1.6	0.31	-0.08	I
	Because I have been here before	8.1	4.8	4.8	80.6	1.6	0.13	-0.10	I
	I feel a sense of participation when obtaining local products	8.1	1.6	6.5	77.4	4.8	0.10	-0.09	I

(A=attractive, M=must be, O=one-dimensional, I=indifferent, R=reverse, Q=questionable, CS= coefficient of satisfaction, DS= coefficient of dissatisfaction)

Table 4: The result of the elements of community cultural product.

The results of the empirical study are presented in Table 4. A relative questionnaire based on the Kano Diagram (see Figure 1) investigated subjects' thinking to determine the quality attributes. According to survey results, the quality attributes were calculated taking into account the number of times a particular quality attribute was cited. And then, the number of qualities identified most frequently became the list quality requirements. The data on "Hand-made by the craftsmen and artists" in attractive, one-dimensional, must-be, and indifferent qualities accounted for about 51.6%, 8.1%, 1.6%, 38.7% respectively; more than 50% of the subjects agreed with the statement that this

element determined an attractive quality. It also determined a "coefficient of satisfaction" and a "coefficient of dissatisfaction" by (a) and (b) formula, accounting for 0.60 and -0.10, respectively. This means that the sufficient "attractive quality" for satisfaction is greater than the insufficient "attractive quality" for the impact of dissatisfaction. Sufficient attractive quality causing user satisfaction is more obvious, indicating that hand-made products by artists possess the attractive quality attribute with high reliability.

The quality of the elements

The results revealed that eight elements of attractive qualities: “Appealing shape”, “Uniqueness”, “Value of collection”, “Natural material”, etc (see Table 4) belonged to the one-dimensional quality. “Quality” signifies that community cultural products need as many elements of quality as possible. This quality and extent of satisfaction will appear in one dimension: when quality is more sufficient, the extent of satisfaction will increase. In the must-be quality, there are “Commemorative value”, “quality assurance” and “local element and features”, meaning that if the quality is insufficient, the extent of dissatisfaction will increase: -0.58, -0.69, and -0.48, respectively. Therefore, users considered the position of community cultural products that include local elements and features to express the diversity between normal products and community cultural products. Moreover, “quality assurance”, and “commemorative value” are “must-be quality” for consumers. The other elements are classified as expressing no difference in the quality of cultural products, whether good or bad, with consumer satisfaction insignificantly affected. This result attests no reverse quality in the quality of classification (see Table 4).

This study, through the Kano quality model analysis of results, contributes to the economic development of the community industry by allowing designers to comprehend the basic needs of consumer products. It clarifies the difference in the requirements of many aspects of quality, and furthermore, was defined and planned according to product quality characteristics through community culture. By determining the needs of attractive quality and enhancing one-dimensional quality, community cultural products increase product satisfaction and create greater product differentiation.

CONCLUSIONS

Cultural products increase users’ pleasure through their daily use. There is a shift in product design from the strictly physical and functional levels to satisfying the emotional needs of consumers. This emotional satisfaction can solidify images of community and local features, thereby enhancing

the value of cultural industries and promoting new opportunities for sustainable development. This paper applied Kano quality attributes to research the qualities of community cultural products and the relationship between these and levels of consumer satisfaction. Therefore, the applications of quality attributes incorporated different qualities.

This study used the Kano model to explore the relationship between product quality attributes and community satisfaction, clarifying the real needs of the community for the consumers of cultural. By the application of quality attributes, understanding consumer demands for different quality categories becomes clarified. The classification of products as attractive, must-be, and one-dimensional quality, indicates that improvement of product quality enhances user satisfaction; different benefits result from different quality categories, providing appropriate prioritization of quality (Chen & Chuang, 2008). Must-be qualities have to be given priority to satisfy consumers; the attractive one-dimensional quality is the priority consideration.

EMOTIONAL EXPERIENCE OF PRODUCTS

This paper takes community cultural products for example to discuss the relationship of “satisfied” evaluations by users and 25 elements of product quality. Using the five elements of the emotional experience of products (Demir & Desmet, 2009) for classification, the results indicate that the 25 elements of community cultural products include: 8 attractive qualities, 3 must-be qualities, 1 one-dimensional quality, and 13 indifferent qualities to link quality and satisfaction between the different qualities, not only the linear qualities in Table 5.

classification	Elements of community cultural products
Attractive quality	Appealing shape
	Uniqueness
	Pleasure
	Creativity
	Value of collection
	Hand-made by the craftsmen and artists
	Hand-made by myself
	Natural material
Must-be quality	Commemorative value
	Quality assurance

	Local element and features
One-dimensional	Quality

Table 5: Community cultural products with attractive, must-be and one-dimensional quality

1. In “noticing a product”, appealing shape, uniqueness, pleasure, and creativity belong to attractive qualities. This means that when users buy certain community cultural products, those qualities will not be considered. On the contrary, when those qualities are sufficient, users will be more delighted or surprised. However, the data of quality “Appealing Shape” in attractive, must-be and one-dimensional quality are very close. The data on satisfaction and dissatisfaction were both more than 50% coefficient, which means that degree of satisfaction will increase when quality is sufficient or insufficient; it also represents that “Appealing Shape” is the users’ purchase priority.
2. In “product usage”, “functionality” “and my need” are both indifferent qualities. This means that whether or not community cultural products are provided with functionality, it does not affect consumer satisfaction and quality requirements. The reason for this is that most community cultural products focus on local elements and materials, especially in regard to hand-made products. Therefore, products provided with the functional needs of the consumer in mind are not all that significant.
3. In “usage episode events”, “local elements and features” is a must-be quality, and “natural materials” is an attractive quality. The most appealing community cultural product is made from natural materials, such as rushes in Miao-li County Court and wheat in Taichung Daya town. We used local elements and features to design many kind of creative products that correspond to the key factors in the development of the cultural creative industry (Hwang, 2002), i.e., enjoying the community in stories, aesthetic perception, value, creation and experience to produce sympathy with local culture and identity.
4. In “an external agent mentioning the product”, only “quality assurance” is a must-be quality; all of the others are indifferent qualities. Media propaganda and guide narration do not directly

produce emotional experiences for users. Each subject felt emotional experiences to a different extent and did not fill in the questionnaire immediately through Media propaganda or guide narration so that objective data was not produced.

5. In “a change in the relationship”, belonging to attractive quality there are “Hand-made by the craftsmen and artists”, and “hand-made by myself”. These results reveal that whatever the craftspeople, artists or users, the features of “hand-made” can add to a product’s attractive quality. Even if this quality is insufficient, it will not reduce the coefficient of consumer satisfaction.

In the future, community cultural industries will be orientated to emphasize features of industrial development. Small quantity, hand-made, local culture and quality are unique characteristics of community products. Furthermore, users may have the same empathy in industry cognition and local brands because of the cultural attributes of community products and by being immersed in emotional experiences. The study was restricted to interviewing only a small sample of users conveying different emotional experiences. The product designers, community operators and community projectors were not analyzed in relation to the accompanying user experiences. A much larger sample representative of the different emotional experiences of users needs to be studied.

NOTES

1. Figure Dolls are from Hong Kong. It was popular to teenagers in Taiwan from 2001 as the latest fashion collection. Figure Dolls restore the memory of the ancient, popular chase, individuality, sub-cultural consciousness and emotions.
2. The Jadeite Cabbage is a piece of jadeite carved into the shape of a Chinese cabbage head, with a locust camouflaged in the leaves. It is part of the collection of the National Palace Museum in Taipei, Taiwan. (Wikipedia, 2011)
3. Nantou is surrounded by hills and has slightly acidity soil that is the best growth environment for black tea in Taiwan. Every household planted black tea and engaged in picking, rolling, fermentation and drying to promote the local economic industry. Moreover, the culture and history of black tea built a brand of Sun Moon Lake.
4. Plant Dyeing Bag is made in Taiwan, Nantou County through a housewife association. Nantou County is the geographic center of Taiwan in the midst of mountains. There are rich forest resources and plant species. Plant dyeing uses plant roots, stems and leaves,

boiled in water until the water is completely colored. Then after dipping in cloth, clothes can be sewn into all kinds of products.

5. The soil in Yuanli Township, Miao-li County is suitable for making bricks, but with the brick industry in decline, brick companies were reformed into a new tourism industry to provide services and products.

6. Wedding Candle Holder is made in Shadow Museum, Kaohsiung County.

7. Brick Card Set is made in Brick & Art Association, Miao-li County.

8. Flower Light is made in Su Ho Memorial Paper Local Museum.

9. The Hakka are Han Chinese who speak the Hakka language and have links to the provincial areas of Guangdong, Guangxi, Sichuan, Hunan and Fujian in China. The cotton prints of Impatiens Package are derived from Hakka culture.

10. Bark Lamp is made from branches and bark in the South Pond Community Development Association, Hualien County.

11. The shape of Spice Jar is that of tofu, famous food in Shenkeng, Taipei County. A local association created the tofu shape as a Spice Jar to reinforce the image.

12. Bowl with Chopsticks is made in Lacquer Art Museum, Taichung County.

13. Brick Charm is made in Brick & Art Association, Miao-li County.

14. Art Cup has a Wild Boar drawn on it, which is a symbol of the Tsou Tribe in Alishan.

15. Health Massager is made from straw in Nantou County, Sandals Pier Culture and Local Education Association.

16. Rush material produced near Miao-li County and community resident make the products by hand to supplement family income.

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